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Perception of Cruise Ship Tourists for Service in the Benoa Port, Bali Indonesia

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Abstract

Service at the seaport as the entrance of cruise ship tourists who come on vacation to various destinations in Bali. Therefore, the facilities at the port of Benoa including at the arrival terminal are part of the first impression that affects the quality of the expectations of cruise ship tourists who will make a visit. Bali is a barometer of Indonesia's tourist destinations developing and renovating port facilities to improve service quality. Foreign tourists who were visited Bali have increased over the past ten years. Not only they access via the Ngurah Rai airport, but many also through the port of Benoa. Guests who choose the port route have own considerations. The port as the first place seen by cruise ship tourists visiting Bali, in fact, there are still many foreign tourists who complain about the quality of service at the Benoa Port of Bali. This study aims to find out the perception of cruise ship tourists who visit Bali about services at the Port of Benoa, Bali. This type of research is descriptive by using a sample was 264 the cruise ship tourists by the purposive sampling technique. The results showed that cruise ship tourists who were visited Bali assessed the service of the Benoa port was good. The highest service dimension in Benoa port is the tangible dimension and the lowest is the empathy dimension.

Keywords: Perception, Cruise Ship, Tourist, Services, Port

1. Introduction

Background

Bali is one of the main tourist destinations in Indonesia with the number of foreign tourists visiting Bali and Indonesia in the last ten years according to data sourced from the provincial statistical body of the province of Bali in 2018, that tourist visits have increased over the past 10 years. Increased tourist visits to Bali occur because of the natural appeal and uniqueness of Balinese culture, various arts, customs, cultural richness and social religious traditions of a society imbued with Hinduism. The great potential has been packaged as a tourist attraction so that Bali is a mainstay of Indonesian tourism by having cultural tourism characteristics, in accordance with Bali Provincial Regulation No. 2 of 2012 concerning Bali Cultural Tourism.

Benoa Harbor as one of the provincial strategic areas has a large position and responsibility in the tourism arena in Bali. Benoa Harbor functions as a passenger, freight, fuel and Tourism Port service. Efforts to strengthen the function of the Benoa Port have been carried out by preparing a master plan and layout of the port covering an area of 58 Ha. Benoa Port Development consists of 3.55 ha of cargo, 65 ha of cabin area, Marina tourism of 3.7 ha, 3.6 ha of offices, 5.6 ha of passenger terminal. Container terminal 2.63 ha. Liquid and gas bulk terminal 4.7 ha, public facilities 3.9 ha, industry 23.2 ha, and roads 2.4 ha. The development of the Benoa port is carried out in an effort to improve services to all parties who will use the Benoa Port.

Cruise tourists who visit Bali have different reasons than tourists who generally use airplanes, therefore these differences in interests need to be bridged and found a good solution. For example, customs, quarantine, and immigration services must certainly carry out their functions as security or inspection sites, as well as services or service points for cruise ship tourists. On the other hand, cruise ship tourists who have long been in the ship want to quickly get out of the harbor to then enjoy Bali and its beauty which will certainly affect tourist satisfaction. The purpose of this study was to determine the perception of cruise ship tourists about service at the port of Benoa.

Research Question and Objective

Base on the background above, the formulation of the problem from this study is what is the opinion of cruise ship tourists regarding the quality of service at Bali's Benoa port? While the purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of Bali Benoa Port service quality on cruise ship tourist satisfaction, then research was conducted at the Benoa Harbor in Bali. The cruise ship chosen as the research destination is a cruise ship anchored at the port of Benoa in Bali originating from various countries with the aim of getting heterogeneous respondents. So, this study aims is to analyze the effect of service quality at the Benoa Port of Bali and analyze the opinion of cruise ship tourists regarding service quality Benoa port of Bali.

2. Literature Review

Meaning of Cruise ship

Cruise ship is a commercially managed accommodation that uses a boat/ship as a facility to get lodging, eating and drinking services, as well as other services for tourists who stay within a certain period of time. The cruise ship tourism industry is categorized into luxury hotels that can be found at sea/ocean, which are often called cruisers, marine hotels or floating hotels (https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kapal_pesiar).

Now a cruise is a favorite accommodation that is much in demand by tourists in enjoying their vacation. Perwani (1997: 6) states floating hotels are forms of accommodation found in river, canal or sea areas with special features, including using boats or ships that sail from one place to another, and have a number of guests certain during a predetermined trip.

While Bagyono (2012: 65), mentioned that a cruise ship (marine hotel) is a floating hotel that provides room facilities, restaurants and bars similar to five-star hotels. This means that the service activities of employees towards tourists who stay on cruise ships are not much different from the service activities that occur at other star-rated hotels on land (resorts). The difference is that tourists who stay in star hotels, they can do or enjoy entertainment activities that occur inside and outside the hotel, such as to tourism destinations. While tourists who live on cruise ships, they can only enjoy entertainment in the cruise ship environment within a certain period.

The cruise ship is a floating hotel that provides accommodation, food and beverage services and other services, including entertainment that is packaged in a tour package. Work carried out by officers who work on cruise

ships includes cleaning services, food and beverage services in restaurants, entertainment services, security, maintenance of ship facilities and so on. The control of the ship's activity is the head of the ship (ship's captain or shipmaster) while the affairs of service for tourists who live on cruise ships by their employees are the responsibility of the hotel manager. There are several large cruise companies that are generally well known in the world, including: Disney Cruise Line, Regent Seven Seas Cruise Line, Viking Line, Cunard, Royal Caribbean Cruise Line, Holland American Line, Norwegian Cruise Line, Queen Mary, Mediterranean Shipping Company, Carnival Cruise Line, and Star Cruise and others.

Service Quality Measurement

Service Quality is the difference between the expectations and the reality of the customers for the service they receive. Service Quality can be known by comparing customer perceptions of the services they actually receive with the services they expect. Quality of service becomes the main thing that is taken seriously by the company, which involves all of the company's resources. Based on the opinion above, it can be concluded that the main factors that affect the quality of service are the expected services and perceived/perceived services. If the perceived service matches the expected service, the quality of the service will be perceived as good or positive. If the perceived service exceeds the expected service, the service quality is perceived as ideal quality.

To facilitate the assessment and measurement of service quality, a service quality measurement tool called SERVQUAL (service quality) was developed. SERVQUAL is a multi-item scale that can be used to measure customer perceptions of service quality which includes five dimensions (Zeithami, 2004). Zeithami (2004) identifies 5 (five dimensions of service quality used by customers in evaluating service quality. The five dimensions are tangible, direct empathy, reliability, responsiveness, responsiveness, and assurance (guarantees), which are described as follows.

1. Tangibles (direct evidence), namely the ability of a company to show its existence to external parties. The appearance and capability of the company's physical facilities and infrastructure and the condition of the surrounding environment are tangible evidence of the services provided by the company.
2. Empathy which gives sincere and individual or personal attention given to customers by trying to understand consumer desires.
3. Reliability is the ability to provide the promised service immediately, accurately, and satisfactorily.
4. Responsiveness is the ability of cruise ship employees to help and provide fast (responsive) and appropriate services to tourists by delivering clear information.
5. Assurance, the existence of certainty that is knowledge, courtesy, politeness and the ability of company employees to foster trust in customers for the services provided by the company.

3. Research Methods

Research methods conducted at Bena port, Bali. This study uses data collection techniques with observation, interviews, questionnaires. The sampling technique used a purposive sampling method of 264 respondents. Descriptive qualitative data analysis method and use a Likert scale measurement. Each of the different weights is very good, good, good enough, not good and not good.

4. Results and Discussion

Perception of Cruise Ship Tourists Who Visit to Bali

In an analysis of services at the Bena port by cruise ship tourists visiting Bali, it is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average Value of Benoa Port Services, Bali Indonesia

No	Dimensions	Mean
1	Tangible	4,19
2	Emphaty	4,11
3	Responsive	4,13
4	Reliability	4,16
5	Assurance	4,13
	Average	4,14

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the average score of statements regarding services at Benoa port is 4.11 which is in the range of 3.41-4.20 which means good. This means that cruise ship tourists who visit Bali assess that service is good.

Tangible of Benoa harbor includes professional, clean, and neat appearance of tasks, complete and modern equipment, clean and comfortable Benoa Harbor environment, cruise ship tourist assistance guide board for information, neat and comfortable room layout. This physical evidence can affect the comfort and fluency in providing services to every cruise ship tourist. This can be seen from the majority of respondents who stated their agreement, meaning that the physical conditions at the Benoa port service were in accordance with the wishes of the tourists.

Empathy of Benoa port services include officers able to understand the needs of cruise ship tourists, officers treat tourists with attentive attention, officers are easily contacted by cruise ship tourists, officers prioritize the interests of tourists, services do not discriminate. The attention of these officers can affect the comfort and fluency in providing services to every cruise ship tourist. This can be seen from the majority of respondents who expressed their agreement, meaning that sincere and individual or personal attention given by the Benoa port met tourists' expectations.

The responsiveness of Benoa port services includes the readiness of the officers in serving cruise ship tourists, the willingness to help tourists, the officers are quick to respond to the cruise ship cruise ship, provide clear information, and are easily understood by cruise ship tours. This responsiveness can affect the comfort and fluency in providing services to every cruise ship tourist. This can be seen from the majority of respondents who stated their agreement, meaning that the ability of officers at the Benoa port to help and provide fast services to the Benoa port meets the expectations of tourists.

The reliability of Benoa port services includes officers working quickly, officers keeping promises, officers are able to provide good and clear information. This reliability can affect the comfort and fluency in providing services to every cruise ship tourist. This can be seen from the majority of respondents who stated their agreement, meaning that the ability of officers at the Benoa port, the ability to provide the promised services immediately, accurately, and satisfactorily can be demonstrated by the Benoa port and meets the expectations of tourists.

Benoa harbor service assurance includes officers able to answer any questions asked by cruise ship tourists, tourists feeling safe and comfortable, friendly and courteous officers so as to foster confidence in cruise ship tourists, officers demonstrate the ability and knowledge of what is done. This can be seen from the majority of

respondents who stated their agreement, meaning that the certainty given by the Bena port could foster trust in cruise ship tourists.

5. Conclusion

The average service score at the port of Bena is 4.11 which is in the range of 3.41-4.20 which means good. Cruise tourists who visit Bali assess the service of the Bena port is good. The highest service dimension at Bena port is the tangible dimension and the lowest is the empathy dimension. In conclusion, the quality of services performed at Bali's Bena Port can be felt well by cruise ship tourists who visit Bali through the Bena port.

References

- Abbot Tashakkori. 2010. Charles Teddlie. *SAGE Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social & Behavioral Research*. California Sage Publication Inc.
- Affecting Tourist Satisfaction and Its Consequences ". *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 1557-1560.
- Agung Kresnamurti. 2011. *Indonesian Science Management Research Methods. Indonesian Science Management Research Journal (JRMSIO)*. Vol. 2, No. 2, 2011.
- ARLI, P. (2014). The effects of Service Quality Perceptions of Turkish Cruise
- Astina, N. G.2017. Dissertation; *The Effect of Quality of Employee Services Based on Local Balinese Wisdom on the Satisfaction and Intention of Loyal Behavior of Foreign Tourists in Non-Star Hotels in Bali*
- Bagyono 2012. *Tourism and Hospitality*. Alfabeta. Bandung Bali
- Bali Province Manpower and Transmigration Office (Disnakertrans)*. 2017.
- Bali Provincial Statistics Agency. *Bali in Numbers - Bali in Figure 2017*.
- Bali Regional Tourism Office (Disparda Bali), 2017. *Bali Tourism Statistics*
- Bambang. S.2013 Development Policy for Tourism Destination Concepts and Its Applications in Indonesia. Yogyakarta 1. Edition: Gava Media Publisher.
- Fornell, C. 1992. *National customer satisfaction barometer: the Swedish Hospitality Industry*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons Corp.pp 43-45. Hospitality Press Pty.
- Hossain, Mohammed Javed. 2012. "Impact of Service Quality on Customer"
- Kevin, Baker., Huyton, Jeremy. 2001. *Hospitality Management: an Introduction*.
- Kotler, Philip and Kevin Lane Keller. 2012. *Marketing Management 13*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Kozak, M. 2001. Repeaters' behavior at two distinct destinations. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 28 (3), 784-807.
- Kozak, Martin and Decrop, Alain. 2009. *Handbook of Tourist Behavior*. New
- Mowen, John, C., and Minor, M. 2010. *Consumer Behavior Volume 1, Fifth Edition*
- Oliver, R. L. 1981. *Measurment and evaluation of satisfaction processes in retail settings*. Journal of Retailing, 57 (3), 25-48.
- Parasuraman, et al. 2009. *Delivering Quality Service*. New York: The Free Press. Responsible Tourism, Pine Book Publisher, Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Indonesia.
- Pizam, A., Neumann, Y., Reichel, A. 1978. *Dimensions of tourist satisfaction*
- Regional Regulation (Perda) Number 2 of 2012 concerning *Perspective Cultural Tourism*. Editor: Gee, C. Y., Co-Editor: Sola, E. F. Madrid, Spain: World Tourism Organization.
- Sarbini. M.B.2018. *Tourism Philosophy A Practical Philosophy Study*. 1st edition. Yogyakarta:
- Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction: The Case of Singapore.
- Thai Vinh V (2015) article on maritime economic & logistics, *The Impact of Port*
- Tjiptono, Fandy and Gregorius Chandra, 2012